

Is all waste rubbish?

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Abstract. Amongst the severe environmental issues faced by modern societies, one of the more pressing ones is the management of the vast volumes of waste produced. The need to connect the school community with society gave us the incentive to create the science project “**Is all waste rubbish**”, whose focus was to increase students’ awareness in relation to current environmental issues in addition to their active participation as citizens of tomorrow. During the project the students were given the opportunity to work on a ‘real world’ problem i.e., the appropriate waste management of both solid and liquid waste and the need for a circular economy, whilst moving away from the rigid boundaries of their school environment and traditional teaching methods. The participants were able to involve their whole families and disseminate their findings with pupils in their school and other local schools.

Introduction

One of the today’s societies predicaments is the management of the vast waste volumes they produce. The greatness of the issue is due to several causes starting from the big increase in size and concentration of the human population all the way to the consumer habits formed during the later years through the traditional growth model of linear economy which deals with waste as sources of water and soil pollution. Specifically, current forecasts put the size of Earth’s population to approximately 9.5 billion by 2050, which in turn will increase the global demand for resources, leading to global economies demanding thrice the number of resources used today to fulfil their needs. The result would be a rapid increase of the carbon footprint due to an increase of CO₂ emissions. The only way to counteract it is reusing natural resources, the adoption of circular economy and the abandonment of the previous outdated and costly linear economy mode [1]. Circular economy contributes to society’s benefit through the management of resources, waste, and the natural capital [2]. It is considered to be an answer hailing from the future, trying to achieve the ideal economy, wherein nothing goes to waste, and everything is reused. This new model requires new methods of collection, production, and consumption and most importantly it demands the active participation of all the economic operators. In societies plagued by the financial crisis, circular economy not only offers environmental benefits but also the opportunity for sustainable growth and reduction of social and economic inequalities whilst all the while respecting the environment [3].

Through the aid of CONNECT for open schooling, within the action “Science with and for Society” (SwafS) of the EU framework programme for research and innovation “HORIZON 2020” the Junior High School of Nea Alikarnassos was given the opportunity to

work on the science- action project “ **Is all waste rubbish?** ”. Through working on the project students were given the opportunity to study circular economy and appropriate ways for both solid and liquid waste management. 30 students from the 3rd year of Junior High school took part in the project along with their family members and several scientists, such as Environmental Chemists, Chemical Engineers, Mechanical Engineers and Biologists. The aim of the teachers in charge of delivering the science project was the education and raising awareness in the students in relation to environmental issues, the main one being the management of the vast volumes of waste produced every day. Throughout the duration of the project (October 2022- April 2023) students were invited to identify issues and suggest solutions, interact with specialists in the field as well as use their own initiative and take action to educate the rest of their school community about circular economy and the proper management of waste. This innovative science-action program formed part of the curriculum topics of chemical pollution and waste management in the Chemistry and Biology 3rd year lessons. The didactical approaches used were: the discovery teaching method which introduces scientific research as part of the act of schooling, the experiential learning method, cooperative teaching, and the problem solving method [4]. The students were able to develop their skills in question editing, data analysis, evidence discussion, claim discussion, drawing conclusions and the creation of group projects.

Timeline

The project comprised of 3 distinct phases namely the CARE phase, the KNOW phase and the Do phase wherein the students initially CARE about the issue, then want to KNOW more about the issue and finally the want to DO something about the issue so they can influence the world around them and build their capacities. [5].

CARE Phase: At first the teachers heading this project presented the scenario the project was based on to the students taking part. Then the students and teacher brainstormed their ideas about chemical pollution and waste management. The students noted the ways they manage the waste their houses generate, the posed their own questions and got involved in the framework of research-based learning related to chemical pollution of soil and water and the appropriate waste management processes. Afterwards, the students were invited to express all their ideas relating to the subject and it was also requested of them to spend time at home discussing with their families firstly about chemical pollution and its effects on the environment and secondly to identify the reasons they choose to use plastic products in their daily life (properties identification). During the next meeting the teachers referred to the circular economy following a video they were shown, and they were asked to have discussions with their family about the circular economy and the importance of recycling. Finally, the students were asked to identify recycling points in the vicinity of their houses.

KNOW Phase: The students were taught about chemical pollution by their teachers with the help of their school handbooks, scholarly articles, educational videos, and presentations by the teachers heading this project. Specifically, the students were taught about the environmental issues created by the accumulation of solid and liquid waste which then led to the chemical

pollution of the soil and water as well as the role of decomposers in the food chain and the geochemical cycles. (carbon cycle, nitrogen cycle). Afterwards, the students were asked to take home a work sheet and use it to identify the amount of waste generated by their household. In the following two tables we present the volumes of general waste and plastic waste generated by students and how they compare to the amounts produced by the general population of Greece and Europe respectively. Data were drawn from WWF Greece ([WWF Greece: Guide for the reduction and recycling of plastics-ertnews.gr](http://www.ertnews.gr))

Table 1. Comparison of plastic waste by weight generated by students and the general Greek and European population.

Waste/Day	Kg/person
Greece	1.4 ^a
Europe	1.36 ^a
Students	0.9

^a According to WWF Greece

Table 2. Comparison of plastic waste by weight generated by students and the general Greek population.

Plastic Waste/Day	g/person
Greece	190 ^a
Students	164

^a According to WWF Greece

During their next meeting the students were taught about polymer – plastics, how they are produced, their advantages and disadvantages and the issues around the fact that they do not decompose in nature. The teachers made use of their school handbooks, scholarly articles, educational videos, and presentations to cover the above topics. For the needs of the project and to better coordinate the work of the team we created an online lesson in e-class titled “**Is all waste rubbish?**” ([Electronic school class \(e-class\) | Is all waste rubbish?... \(sch.gr\)](http://www.sch.gr)) which included work sheets and useful websites that the students could utilise to further study waste management. Moreover, all members of the team were given the opportunity to pose their questions, make remarks and share their ideas throughout the project. Students then studied different types of plastic packaging and learned how to identify the polymer they were made of using the special identification symbol present on them. Following that, students were asked, using different types of plastic products they could find in their households, to collect any relevant information about the different types of plastic and the time it takes for each of them to decompose in nature. Lastly, a discussion was held about the results of their projects where their main conclusion was the importance of the circular economy and the need to avoid the linear economy.

During the KNOW phase the scientists that taught the students about the environmental issues of scenario of the project played an integral part. The students first met a scientist during their visit to the CRETAquarium “Thalassokosmos”. They watched the 2-hour scientific

programme “Exploring a marine threat” which allowed them to study the marine pollution caused by plastics and micro plastics. They interacted with a marine biologist employed by HCMR (Hellenic centre for Marine Research) who presented them with data about marine pollution. The students learned how to identify plastic packaging, how to separate microplastics from the sand using a stereoscope and finally calculated the percentage composition of microplastics in a sand sample from a nearby beach. The scientist also highlighted the effects of marine chemical pollution to the different ecosystems and marine organisms and explained how the phenomenon of bioaccumulation poses a major threat to humans since they are the final consumer in food chains. Another meeting took place, this time with a Chemical Engineer, of the Unified Waste Management Association of Crete (also known as ESDAK), at school. The subject of the meeting was “Waste management in the context of circular economy”, the students were presented with the full array of the different waste management programmes ESDAK is implementing, based on EU guidance, all aiming at the reduction of Crete’s environmental footprint. The students were introduced to different waste management projects and innovative actions for their management, such as the programme LIFE F4F (FOOD for FEED) which aims to utilise the organic waste generated from hotels for the preparation of animal feed, the pilot programme A2UFOOD for the production of bio-plastics from organic residue and the autonomous robotic system for recycling. Additionally, they learned about new initiatives that will be introduced shortly in the city such as recycling spots, recycling corners, and compensatory recycling houses. The 3rd meeting was with a Mechanical Engineer of the Public Water Supply and Sewerage Company of Heraklion (DEWAH) and its subject was Heraklion’s wastewater treatment. The students visited the biological wastewater treatment plant in Finikia. They learned that part of the treated wastewater is used for the irrigation of the surrounding agricultural areas and the remainder is disposed in the sea without any risks to the marine environment. Moreover, biogas generators are used to harness the methane generated by the sewage treatment to cover the majority of the energy needs of the plant. On the same day, they also visited the production unit of the pilot program for the production of bio-plastic from organic residue A2UFOOD.

DO phase: As part of their actions following their visit to the Crete Aquarium, the students spend some time clearing all accumulated waste out of the neighbouring beach. Using some of the recyclable materials they collected, they created handicrafts inspired by the threat plastics pose to sea turtles. Following an information session by one of the scientists working for the Unified Waste Management Association of Crete (ESDAK), they created a recycling corner at their school (Figure 1) and held their own information sessions for their fellow students. They collected photos, articles and weblinks about the circular economy and the actions Greece takes with regards to it and how it compares to the rest of Europe. After that they uploaded everything to the online magazine “OIKO- ENERGO”(schoolpress.sch.gr/oikoenergo/), which was created for the needs of the program. Using the programs Adobe Illustrator and Photoshop the students created a poster (Figure 2) to disseminate their project to the public. Additionally, they sent a letter to the mayor on the need to inform the public about recycling and the importance of circular economy. They also send some of the posters they created and suggested they were displayed around the City Hall and wherever else he deemed necessary on the occasion of World Environment Day. Lastly, the students worked on group projects which, along with the rest of their actions, were presented at CONNECT student conference.

Figure 1. Recycling corner.

Conclusions

During our science- action project “Is all waste rubbish?” our students learned about the circular economy and the need to recycle. They had discussions with their families and made the decision to adapt their environmental habits, those that were not recycling before having now started doing so and those that were already actively recycling have hereon intensified their efforts. They adopted the desired stages of circular economy and became ambassadors of those matters to the rest of the students and local community. They met with experts and were given the opportunity to discuss about the chemical pollution currently affecting both water and soil as well as being able to pose their own question to the experts. This process was greeted with great enthusiasm from the children due to the opportunities they had to receive immediate answers to their questions and made them desire new knowledge outside the one offered through their textbooks. Furthermore, the students especially enjoyed their family’s involvement to the learning process since they all worked together to calculate the amount of waste they were generating and then compared it to the amounts generated in the rest of Greece and Europe. Also, they calculated the amount of plastic waste they each generated and were made aware of the indiscriminate use of plastics throughout most of the products we use in our everyday life, which lead them to aim to modify their daily habits to better serve the planet and to challenge their families to behave similarly. Finally, they claimed they learned more through the projects and aids they created to disseminate their knowledge to the rest of the school and local community.

Figure 2. Poster created by the students for dissemination of the project to the public.

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